

Sphinx as a Tool for Documenting Technical Projects

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Abstract—Documentation is a vital part of a technical project, yet is sometimes overlooked because of its time-consuming nature. A successful documentation system can therefore benefit relevant organizations and individuals. The focus of this paper is to summarize the main features of *Sphinx*: an open-source tool created to generate *Python* documentation formatted into standard files (HTML, PDF and ePub). Based on its results, this research recommends the use of *Sphinx* for the more efficient writing and managing of a project’s technical documentation.

Keywords—project, documentation, *Python*, *Sphinx*.

1 INTRODUCTION

In a technologically advanced and fast-paced modern society, computer-stored data is found in immense quantities. Writers, researchers, journalists and teachers – to name but a few relevant fields – have acknowledged the issue of dealing with ever-increasing quantities of data. The data can appear in many forms. Therefore, most computer-literate, modern professionals welcome software (or hardware) that aids them in managing and collating substantial amounts of data formats.

All technical projects produce a large quantity of documents, which remain the only elements produced until other deliverables are generated (such as patents, software programs, plans, etc.). This information is consulted both at management level and by team members who are working on the project. There are three possible situations which highlight the importance of these documents within an organisation (Rakos et al., 2005):

a) If a team member leaves the current project, they will be replaced by another member who must use the documentation passed on by their predecessor. If the documentation does not exist or is deficient, the new member will require more time to learn how to carry out the task assigned to them.

b) When the team progresses to a different phase in a project, documentation is the preferred method for exchanging information between teams, regardless of whether they also have complementary communication methods or not.

c) Occasionally, projects can be delayed or suspended for a variety of reasons, such as lack of financial support. When resuming a project, it is necessary to analyse the most recent documentation and check the status of the project. In the case of missing or a lack of documentation, tasks could be needlessly repeated, therefore wasting time.

The documenting of a program’s source code is a process that has been well received and considered an efficient programming practice (McConnell, 1993). However, it has not always been favoured by programmers, due to a lack of time or a simple tool to complete such a complex task. Documen-

tation is encouraged in the field of programming because it gives the programmer a copy of their previous work. Furthermore, it helps other programmers to modify their coding, and it benefits the pooling of information within an organization.

Software documentation should be focused on transmitting information that is useful and meaningful rather than information that is precise and exact (Forward and Lethbridge, 2002). Software tools are used to document a program’s source code. This article presents the *Sphinx* [1] tool from a practical point of view, and its use as a documentation system in technical projects. A description of its main features and possible requirements that may arise during the documentation process are detailed below.

2 SPHINX

2.1 Overview

Sphinx [1] is a documentation generation software which converts “reStructuredText” [2] (henceforth, ReST) mark-up language files into HTML web pages (including Windows help files), as well as other formats such as PDF or ePub. Therefore, the user can write pages in ReST, whose syntax is simple but, much like *Python* [3], is sensitive to indentation.

FIGURE 1. Logotype of the *Sphinx* tool.

The tool’s logotype is based on the Egyptian symbol of the eye of Horus, in keeping with the program’s name (Figure 1). George Brandl created *Sphinx* in 2008 to document the programming language of *Python* (Brandl, 2017). As the tool has a BSD license, it has been used not only to document *Python* code in important projects such as *Scipy* [4] (scientific library) and *Matplotlib* [5] (data plotting library), but also to document other languages, and even for

online book publications. With appropriate modifications, the tool has also been used to write personal blogs. However, the use of *Pelican* [6] is more appropriate in this situation, as it is a static website generator in *Python* with functions suitable for blogging.

Sphinx is an important part of a software’s architecture in terms of the signac framework project, “which provides functionality for operating on data spaces common to a variety of computational workflows” (Adorf et al., 2016). The writers of *Sphinx* recognise that the signac framework is implemented in *Python* (tested for versions 2.7.x and 3.x.), and that the package, which has a very high test coverage – is documented using the *Sphinx* documentation tool.

As a part of the *Python* framework, *Sphinx* can also be used to manage data from weather reports – and has thus met the needs of the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement Climate Research Facility (Helmus and Collis, 2016). The role of *Sphinx* within this framework, as its writers explain, is to extract the *docstrings* from the source code and format them using the *numpydoc* extension.

The principal role of this tool is as an organisational feature. Simply put, *Sphinx* can turn an untidy number of HTML files into a well-organised and user-friendly system that is easy to navigate. As Brandl (2017) explains, from the same source, the tool can also create a LaTeX file that can configure a PDF version of the documents, or make a PDF file directly by using *rst2pdf*. Although *Sphinx* offers support for API docs, “the focus is on hand-written documentation”.

2.2 Installation

The *Sphinx* tool is periodically updated and its most recent version is 1.5 (December, 2016). There are similar tools available on the market for documenting code, for example, *Natural Docs* [7] and *Doxygen* [8]. Currently, online technical documentation can be carried out through more important lightweight mark-up languages, for example ReST or Markdown. There is some debate over which language is better, but the syntaxes are similar and are both widely used. Before beginning the installation of *Sphinx*, it is necessary to have the *Python* programming language installed on one’s computer in either of its two development branches (2.x or 3.x). The installation process of *Sphinx* is similar in both the Windows and Linux operating systems, as this tool can be conventionally installed using the `pip` command in *Python* or from the *Anaconda* [9] distribution.

The tool is started using the command `sphinx-quickstart` from a terminal window. To create a new documentation project, the administrator user must complete a questionnaire that appears on the screen, indicating the project name, its root directory and which modules or specific extensions will be used, etc. This information is saved in a file with a configuration called `config.py`, which can be modified later. As a result of executing the previous command, the “Source” and “Build” folders are created. The strict source code is included in the aforementioned configuration file and in a master ReST document called `index.rst`. The master document is the welcome or cover page, and shows, among other elements, the table of contents linking the main page to the ReST pages. During the documentation process, the administrator or the collabo-

rating users will add ReST pages to the “Source” folder. Additionally, the pages generated from the ReST files are saved as HTML files in the “Build” folder, alongside all the files required for its correct visualization, such as images and documents, Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and javascript files (JS).

2.3 Design

Sphinx has a wide variety of templates, allowing the content to be adapted to one’s needs. These templates are generally designed so that the contents can be viewed correctly on mobile devices. In addition, a template can also be created from scratch, or, more simply, an existing template can be modified in terms of its design or functions according to one’s needs. The *OpenCV* project uses a default template provided by *Sphinx* for its documentation page (Figure 2). The content blocks are as to be expected in a template: header, sidebar, main and footer.

FIGURE 2. Documentation home page of the *OpenCV* project.

To create or modify a template, an understanding of CSS, HTML, JS, and, to a lesser extent, some insight into *Python* are required for implementing a more complex functionality. In most cases, design changes will be limited to modifications within the CSS file, which basically determines the page’s dimensions and content blocks, as well as other graphic features (colours, images and text format). To facilitate the layout of a template, the *Mozilla Firefox* or *Chrome* browsers can be used with Nicolas Huon’s *CSSViewer* or a similar CSS properties viewer.

2.4 Content

This section includes an example of a code that follows the typical syntax of a page in the ReST format; the in which way to add content through *Sphinx*. Frequently used elements are incorporated into this code such as titles, subtitles, paragraphs, commentaries, text formatters (italics and bold), tables and lists.

```

This is a main title
=====
Here is a paragraph.
.. This is a comment Section

Title
-----
Another paragraph, but inside the section.
This sentence is in italics and this one is in bold. Below, a one row table
with three columns is shown.

+-----+-----+-----+
| 1 | 2 | 3 |
+-----+-----+-----+

* This is a bulleted list.
* Second item.

1. This is a numbered list.
2. It has two items too.

#. This is a numbered list.
#. It has two items too.

```

The result of transforming the previous code into HTML and ePub is shown in Figures 3a and 3b, respectively.

a) HTML

b) ePub

As the examples display, the syntax is legible in flat file and, once the output document is created (for example, HTML), the contents are correctly visualized according to the hierarchy of titles, the numbering of the lists, as well as text format. It is also possible to add in more complex content structures such as tables.

Different types of files can be created from a single source code with the `make` command. In the help section of this command, a list of the output files which can be generated is provided (see Table 1).

TABLE 1. Commands and its description.

Command	Description
applehelp	to make an Apple Help Book
devhelp	to make HTML files and a Devhelp project epub to make an epub
dirhtml	to make HTML files called index.html in directories
epub	to make an ePub
html	to make standalone HTML files
htmlhelp	to make HTML files and an HTML help project
json	to make JSON files
pickle	to make pickle files
qthelp	to make HTML files and a qthelp project
latex	to make LaTeX files, you can set PAPER=a4 or PAPER=letter
man	to make manual pages
singlehtml	to make a single large HTML file
text	to make text files

To publish the content, that is, to convert the ReST pages to HTML, the `make html` command must be used. In the ‘compilation’ step, alerts may appear that interrupt the process. These are usually the result of an unpermitted syntax in the ReST pages. With the development of eBooks and other portable reading devices (tablets and smartphones), the current trend is to generate .pdf files and ePubs, the latter in particular. These are two options available within the program.

2.5 Main Features

Although some characteristics of the program have progressed, such as the types of output files (HTML, PDF and ePub), this tool also allows the use of LaTeX. The documents generated have an ideal format and structure for use on electronic devices, because, among other reasons, cross-references can be added to the content (citations, glossaries of terms, etc.). Also, there is an automatic numbering of titles or other elements such as figures or tables, mathematical formulas (in the `sphinx.ext.mathjax` extension)

FIGURE 3. Example of (a) HTML and (b) ePub file.

and the programming of language source codes. It is interesting to add HTML code directly into a page in ReST format as it adds more flexibility to the tool.

Regarding content organization, there is a table of contents, called `toctree`, which can be continually displayed on the main page (`index.rst`) and/or in its side block. Another fundamental element of navigating *Sphinx* is the horizontal navigation menu, which usually appears at the top of the page and is called the breadcrumb. This menu proves useful to the reader in terms of always being able to identify where they are.

In terms of the recovering information, the tool's powerful internal search engine, which facilitates fast and precise access to the information, is particularly noteworthy.

As stated above, *Sphinx* was created to document *Python* code source, so it has a specific extension, `sphinx.ext.autodoc`, for automatically generating the *Python* code documentation from its commentaries (called *docstrings*). The tool is compatible with other programming languages, such as C++, if a specific module is installed for that purpose.

Sphinx also allows extensions and modules for integration in the pages and web services *Google Maps*, *Google Analytics*, *Youtube* videos and *Slideshare* type presentations.

2.6 Web Hosting

If we consider that information, internal or external, is a key strategic element within organizations, the way electronic documentation is produced and how it is accessed are therefore crucial factors. Documentation generated by *Sphinx* can be directed to an internal or external audience of the organization. In the case of the former, it is only necessary to reserve a specific directory to upload the documentation, or to simply create a mailing list. In terms of the latter, it is necessary to have web hosting that allows access to the information from outside the organization.

The *Sphinx* tool differs from other content management systems (CMS) such as Wordpress [10] or Drupal [11] in that it does not require a MySQL database to store the information or a PHP for its operation. For *Sphinx* to work, it needs a basic web hosting as only static pages (HTML) and CSS and JS files are uploaded to the server. This results in highly accessible pages, as well as other benefits such as simplified maintenance and improved security. Web hosting is also considerably more economical and inclusive. One might opt for free and widely used services such as *Github* [12] or *Bitbucket* [13] platforms. To use the development platforms as a host, it is necessary to configure the domain (specifically, the DNS) and the platform account to link the domain to a specific directory on the platform. Each time an action is carried out, the documentation updates through the approval of changes made, and so the pages can immediately be updated. This type of platform and the *Sphinx* tool are designed to get the most out of collaborative work.

3 DISCUSSION

In all developmental phases of a technical project, documents are created in various formats (such as; text documents, spreadsheets, plans, images, program source codes, etc.). To integrate these documents into *Sphinx* documenta-

tion, the most important content can be converted to ReST format. Alternatively, the documents can be referenced within the pages, which is the simplest option for documents with a certain extension. The tool should be used as a way of showing useful information without falling into the trap of showing a large quantity of information which could be better consulted in its conventional format (for example, PDF). Additionally, it is possible to include videos and presentations, which allows the content to be more instructional and attractive for the end user. Recordings or presentations made by the company in meetings, congresses, and other events can be incorporated as well. These forms of information are ideal for viewing on smartphones, capitalizing upon the fact that the design responds to these forms of media.

Various independent documentation projects can be created, according to the size and scope of the technical project, the project team, and the project duration. Each documentation project will be managed by an administrator and/or by the contributing users. Despite being a collaborative tool, *Sphinx* does not allow managing permission for groups of users as in wiki type tools, which distinguishes between different user profiles (administrator, contributing user and reader). To partially resolve this circumstance, the administrator can choose to review each edit made to the content before these changes are made permanent.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The *Sphinx* tool is flexible and powerful due to its wide range of functionalities. It enables the efficient organizing and accessing of information, putting emphasis on content before design and scalability. In addition, it is a free tool with a large development community behind it.

The future of *Sphinx* is promising, it is becoming increasingly prevalent in organisations, meeting their needs in the ways presented in this article. Part of its success is due to it being programmed in *Python*, a programming language that is currently in high demand. It is also relatively simple to create and administrate web pages compatible with mobile devices as well as adapting to the corporate design of an organization.

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LINKS

Links are numbered in the order in which they appear in the paper. All websites have been accessed on March 27th, 2017.

1. <http://www.sphinx-doc.org/>
2. <http://docutils.sourceforge.net/rst.html>
3. <https://www.python.org/>
4. <https://www.scipy.org/>
5. <http://www.matplotlib.org/>
6. <http://docs.getpelican.com/>
7. <http://www.naturaldocs.org/>
8. <http://www.stack.nl/~dimitri/doxygen/>
9. <https://www.continuum.io/why-anaconda/>
10. <https://es.wordpress.org/>
11. <https://www.drupal.org/>
12. <https://github.com/>
13. <https://bitbucket.org/>